

Importance of prenatal diagnosis and multidisciplinary care in orofacial cleft: Report of three cases. Embryology understanding and risk factors

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Abstract

Orofacial clefts are common, severe craniofacial malformations. Fetal anatomy assessment is able to detect fetal face defects as early as the first trimester ultrasound scan. The aim of our study is to highlight the importance of prenatal diagnosis. We present three cases of orofacial clefts diagnosed at different times after conception by ultrasound examination. 2D and 3D US assessments were performed, and in addition to the cleft palate, a cleft lip was present, which was not visible earlier due to the limitation of the earliest gestational age. Counseling with oral and maxillofacial surgery specialists was obtained, and the delivery took place in a tertiary hospital. Assessment of risk factors that increase the likelihood of orofacial cleft as well as an accurate prenatal diagnosis are essential for timely management by a multidisciplinary care team.

Keywords

facial clefts, risk factors, multidisciplinary care, ultrasound assessment, prenatal diagnosis

Introduction

Cleft palate and lip are relatively common congenital maxillofacial deformities with a rate of 7.94 per 10,000 live births (Tanaka et al. 2012).

Cleft lip (CL) isolated or in association with cleft palate is more common in males, while isolated cleft palate is more common in females, 0.4:1000 live births. (Mulliken 2004). Although the distribution of clefts varies by area, it is estimated to be 20%–25% CL, 40%–50% CLP (cleft

lip and palate), and 30%–35% CP (cleft palate). (Smarius et al. 2017). Clefts occur in a ratio of 6:3:1: unilateral left, unilateral right, and bilateral (Fraser 1970). The etiology of clefts is multifactorial and involves an interaction between genetics and the environment during embryonic development (Merritt 2005). Several genes have been identified as associated with this malformation; the function and nature vary widely, illustrating the high complexity in the development of the orofacial region (Awotoye et al. 2022b). There are over 400 different syndromes described

in which cleft lip and palate is one of their symptoms. This is due to chromosomal aberrations or monogenic diseases, which can occur in about 30% of orofacial cleft cases (Rogers 1976; Muñoz 2001; Babai and Irving 2023; López-Verdín et al. 2024).

A polygenic accumulation with threshold expression is the basis for the occurrence of an isolated (non-syndrome) cleft lip or palate.

Nonsyndromic cleft lip and palate usually result from the interaction of genetic and environmental factors. Nonmodifiable factors (gender, race, family history, etc.) and modifiable factors (health status, alcohol, diet, medications, etc.) may have an effect in the first two months after conception (Smarius et al. 2017; Paaske and Garne 2018; Awotoye et al. 2022a; López-Verdín et al. 2024).

In recent years, several studies have identified various risk factors associated with cleft lip and palate during the first months of pregnancy: tobacco, alcohol, medication, drugs, infections with viruses and bacteria with mutagenic effects, genetic changes and mutations, and exposure to occupational risk factors. A number of socioeconomic factors may also have an influence (Smarius et al. 2017; Paaske and Garne 2018; Awotoye et al. 2022b; López-Verdín et al. 2024).

Because congenital clefts typically occur in the facial region where normal fusion of structures has not occurred during a specific critical time in embryonic development, knowledge of their location can help the fetal morphologist more accurately and specifically diagnose these clefts. The multifactorial nature of this condition makes prevention difficult and management challenging for the multidisciplinary team (Paaske and Garne 2018; Parham et al. 2023).

The aim of our article is to present a clinical case of an isolated, unilateral cleft lip and palate and to highlight the importance of early diagnosis of orofacial clefts by fetal morphology, proper identification and assessment of risk factors, and determination of therapeutic behavior.

Description of the clinical cases

First case

A 32-year-old nulliparous patient with no underlying health conditions was referred for her first routine ultrasound examination at 12 weeks post conception at Dr. Shterev Hospital, Sofia; Fetal Medicine Unit (Fig. 1 A, B). The diagnosis of a cleft palate was immediately suspected with the use of a systematic approach to the assessment of the fetal profile, where the maxilla was found interrupted in a sagittal plane, and therefore a subsequent scan was offered in the second trimester. Then a 2D and a 3D ultrasound assessment were performed, and in addition to the suspected cleft palate, a cleft lip was present, which was not visible earlier due to the limitation of the early gestational age (Fig. 2 A, B).

No medical condition or risk factors were obtained from the patient's history (no smoking or secondhand smoke exposure, no infections during the pregnancy, no medication (antibiotics, anticoagulants, etc.), or toxins or drug use/abuse were detected. The absence of environmental risk factors underscores the multifactorial nature of cleft development, where genetic predisposition may play a critical role. It is discovered that the cleft is not part of a genetic syndrome; therefore, we establish that the cause of the defect is polygenic association. After counseling with oral and maxillofacial surgery specialists, a treatment plan was made, and the delivery took place in a tertiary hospital. A decision was made to operate on the cleft lip between 3 and 6 months after birth, as well as the cleft uvula and soft palate. The correction of the hard palate will be done between 3 and 6 years of age parallel with long-term continuous orthodontic treatment. Guidelines were given to the parents about the specific care of a child with a cleft in terms of nutrition. It was explained that the treatment of this condition is done by a multidisciplinary team – surgeon, orthodontist, speech therapist, psychologist, etc.

Figure 1. A. Ultrasound image at 12 weeks of gestation. Midsagittal view demonstrating maxillary gap; B. An axial view of a cleft palate at 12 weeks.

Figure 2. Ultrasound images at 20 weeks of gestation. **A.** Coronal view of a fetus with a unilateral cleft lip; **B.** Axial view of a fetus with a unilateral cleft palate.

Second case

A 35-year-old nulliparous patient with no concomitant diseases was referred for her second routine ultrasound examination at 20 weeks post conception at Dr. Shterev Hospital, Sofia; Fetal Medicine. A bilateral cleft lip and palate was seen well with a 2D and 3D rendered image. (Fig. 3) No medical condition or risk factors were identified from the patient's history (no smoking or secondhand smoke exposure, no infections during the pregnancy, no medication (antibiotics, anticoagulants, etc.), or toxins or drug use/abuse were detected. Family history was clear

without any hereditary diseases. The parents were referred for consultation with a maxillofacial and plastic surgeon for the establishment of a treatment plan.

Third case

A 31-year-old woman was referred to Dr. Shterev Hospital, Sofia; Fetal Medicine Unit at 20 weeks post-conception, and until then the patient's antenatal examination was unremarkable. A diagnosis of no syndromic unilateral complete cleft lip (Fig. 4) was made with a 3D rendered image. Medical history revealed any underlying conditions. It was ex-

Figure 3. Coronal view of a fetus with a bilateral cleft lip and palate.

Figure 4. 3D imaging of a fetus with a cleft lip at 20 weeks of gestation.

plained to parents that the cleft lip has multifactorial genesis, and due to the absence of risk factors, it could be a result of a polygenic effect. They were referred for consultation with a maxillofacial surgeon and plastic surgeon, where a multidisciplinary approach is essential for proper management.

Discussion

Orofacial clefts are craniofacial malformations that can present as cheiloschisis (cleft lip/labium leporinum), palatoschisis (cleft palate foux (labium) loupine), or cheilognathopalatoschisis (combined cleft lip, alveolar crest, and palate). According to classification, they could be unilateral or bilateral, complete or incomplete clefts – the tissue defect occupies up to 2/3 of the lip, while with complete lip clefts, it reaches the nostril and often covers the anterior part of the nasal floor (Tanaka et al. 2012; Smarius et al. 2017). In the presented cases, detected orofacial clefts are complete unilateral cleft of the lip, alveolar crest, and hard and soft palate; bilateral cleft of the lip and palate; and complete unilateral cleft of the lip.

Risk factors related to this malformation could be grouped into several categories: hereditary family history, socio-economic, maternal and paternal risk factors; habits and medicines during pregnancy; environmental factors (Merritt 2005; Smarius et al. 2017). In the cases we present, no risk factors on the mother's side were found, the cleft is non-syndromic, and we assume that malformation is the result of polygenic accumulation with threshold expression.

A study identified a novel risk locus on chromosome 8p22 with genome-wide significant joint and GxSex interaction effects (Awotoye et al. 2022a). The hereditary family history in most articles does not mention whether it is on the maternal or paternal side, leaving aside the branch of the genealogy affected by this malformation. A study reported in 2001 revealed that cases of cleft lip and palate were twice as common in families with a hereditary family history of the malformation (Muñoz et al. 2001). In these cases, prevention and genetic counseling are extremely important. We did not make any genetic assessment of mothers or fathers, as there is no family anamnesis for any hereditary diseases in all the cases.

During pregnancy, various factors can influence the fusion of the growths during embryogenesis in the formation of the lips and palate. (Angulo-Castro et al. 2017; Garland et al. 2020). Influence of the father before conception may be due to exposure to toxic substances, which can affect spermatogenesis and even lead to genetic mutations; for example, smoking (Altoé et al. 2020) or other epigenetic changes in sperm nucleic acids may be caused by the influence of environmental factors (Donkin and Barrès 2018).

Surprisingly, in several manuscripts (González et al. 2008; Angulo-Castro et al. 2017; Mejia et al. 2020), a higher proportion of parents (father and mother) are found under the age of 30, in contrast to the results of previous studies, where the influence of age on the risk of cleft lip and palate increases as one of the parents gets older and decreases if one of the parents is young (Bille et al. 2005;

Pérez-González et al. 2023). Similar results were obtained in a Nigerian population (James et al. 2020). In our case, all parents were older than 30 years old.

It has been established worldwide that taking folic acid (4 mg) 3 months before conception by both partners and in the first 3 months of pregnancy reduces the risk of malformations. (López-Verdín et al. 2024). In the presented cases, the three women took 4 mg of folic acid after they had found they were pregnant.

Body mass index (BMI) has only been studied in mothers of cases we presented, and it was in the normal value. In the literature, a clear association with cleft lip and palate and body mass index is observed – most mothers were overweight before, during, and after the pregnancy in question (López-Verdín et al. 2024). No obesity was detected in the presented cases.

Tobacco and alcohol consumption are the factors found to have the greatest association with cleft lip and palate. However, most studies have focused primarily on the mother, with few studies reporting this habit in both parents (Angulo-Castro et al. 2017; López-Verdín et al. 2024). In our cases the mothers were non-smokers, but we have no information on whether the fathers were smokers.

Some authors have argued that tobacco use in men before insemination increases the risk of nonsyndromic orofacial fissures (Altoé et al. 2020; Martinelli et al. 2020). However, these factors appear more frequently in parents of children with cleft lip and palate.

Various authors have indicated that the pattern and severity of malformations caused by drug use depend on the dose, timing, and duration of exposure, with the first trimester of pregnancy being at highest risk. When taking medication in the first months of pregnancy, the risk of having a child with a cleft lip and palate is five times higher. This factor has been found in more than half of mothers (Suazo 2022; Pérez-González et al. 2023). No medication and drug abuse nor exposure to X-rays or environmental risk factors was detected in the cases we described.

Environmental risk factors have not been extensively analyzed in the literature; however, parents exposed to pollution are predisposed to having children with this malformation. According to various authors, increased exposure to solid urban waste increases the rate of cleft lip and palate, as does exposure to toxic substances in the environment and in the workplace, such as wood smoke, chlorinated solvents, fertilizers, and pesticides (Pérez-González et al. 2023). Exposure to both maternal and paternal environmental pollutants such as lead, cadmium, carbon dioxide, cyanide, arsenic, nickel, and mercury is associated with birth malformations and is found in moderate to high amounts in urban areas. (Gasca-Sanchez et al. 2019). All parents were living in Sofia as a capital town with a lot of pollution.

These birth defects are multifactorial, and the prevention is difficult since the fusion of the palatine and labial processes occurs at a time when the mother usually does not yet know that she is pregnant. Therefore, it is necessary to increase health literacy and, when planning a pregnancy, strictly follow the advice of specialists.

The development of facial morphology occurs during the first trimester, characterized by specific processes of fusion among facial swellings. The formation of the lip begins with the fusion of the medial nasal processes, while the palate develops from the primary and secondary palates.

Facial morphology is established in the formation of five facial prominences that surround the primitive oral cavity – the frontonasal prominence, the paired maxillary prominences, and the paired mandibular prominences – and their fusion between the 4th and 10th weeks after conception, with the formation of the upper lip beginning at 24 days after conception and completed at 37 days (Larsen 2009; Sperber et al. 2010; Moore and Persaud 2013).

During the 5th week of embryogenesis, the nasal component of the frontonasal protrusion forms two bilateral ectodermal thickenings called nasal placodes, while during the 6th week, the two medial nasal processes fuse to form the midline of the nose, the medial part of the upper lip, the philtrum, the incisors, and the primary palate. The primary palate is the part of the palate that is located ventral to the foramen incisivum, while the secondary palate is the part located dorsal to the foramen incisivum. The lateral nasal process subsequently forms the alae nasi and the alar base. In the 6th week, the maxillary processes on each side of the mouth grow forward and fuse with the medial nasal processes, resulting in the formation of the lateral upper lip, most of the maxilla, and the secondary palate (Merritt 2005).

Failure of fusion between any of the processes leads to facial clefts and can occur unilaterally or bilaterally and is usually localized between the lateral incisor and the first premolars.

Palatogenesis begins at the end of the 5th week, and palate development is complete by about the 12th week after conception.

If the process of fusion of the palate, which occurs between the 9th and 12th weeks of pregnancy, is disrupted by genetic, mechanical, or teratogenic factors, a secondary cleft palate results.

Routine fetal morphology assessments during the first trimester ultrasound screening can identify these anomalies, and as a case, we present accurate 3D fetal morphology that can precisely diagnose and help the future treatment plan (Larsen 2009; Sperber et al. 2010; Moore and Persaud 2013).

CP is the category most commonly associated with additional congenital anomalies, and the prevalence of associated malformations with CP ranges from 22.2% to 78.3% (Smarius et al. 2017).

Antenatally isolated CP is usually difficult to diagnose, and associated anomalies are reported in 39.1%–66.0% of fetuses with CLP (Maarse et al. 2011, Maarse et al. 2012). This high rate probably reflects many different factors: intrauterine mortality from associated syndromes such as trisomy 13 or 18, pregnancy termination for severe malformations, and the higher possibility of diagnosing CL/P in the presence of multiple associated anomalies, especially if routine screening evaluation is not detailed and comprehensive (Yang and Chang 2024). Evaluation

of the upper lip for possible CL/P is an optional element and has a sensitivity of 88% for detecting CL/P (Maarse et al. 2012). The overall sensitivity for these cleft malformations is lower, as the prenatal detection rate for CP is only 0%–1.4% (Maarse et al. 2011; Maarse et al. 2012).

Modern ultrasound views provided by the expert in prenatal OFC diagnosis include imaging of the posterior edge of the hard palate and the posterior part of the soft palate, and misdiagnosis is minimized. The complete CLP includes the lip, alveolus, primary palate, and the entire secondary palate from the foramen incisivum to the involvement of the uvula. In complete CLP, lip involvement is relatively easy to be detected by ultrasound, while the alar base is characteristically lateralized away from the cleft as in the cases we describe. Different techniques, such as the oblique face view or the inverted face view, make for better 3-D visualization of the alar base (Maarse et al. 2011; Smarius B. et al. 2017; Yang and Chang 2024).

In the first and second case presented, the diagnosis of a cleft palate was suspected at the end of the first trimester with the use of a systematic approach to the assessment of the fetal profile, where the maxilla was found interrupted in a sagittal plane. Therefore, a subsequent scan was offered in the second trimester, where the cleft lip was detected as well. In the third case, the complete unilateral cleft lip was detected within a 3D ultrasound examination. However, in cases of isolated finding, this remains a low-risk structural defect and is due to the polygenic association of the defect (Sperber et al. 2010; Babai and Irving 2023).

It is also very stressful for the parents from an emotional point of view, keeping in mind that 15% of parents leave the child after it is born (Alinezhad et al. 2005). This is why prenatal diagnosis is so important – it determines whether the cleft is part of a syndrome or not, whether there are any accompanying abnormalities, it gives time to plan surgical treatments or other interventions during the pregnancy or immediately after, and it also gives the choice to terminate the pregnancy if it is a symptom of severe genetic syndromes. It also provides time for parents to prepare emotionally and psychologically for the additional care they must provide, especially for feeding – a special pacifier with a palate obturator. Prenatal diagnosis makes parents better prepared to accept the waiting time between birth and the first corrective surgical intervention (Grollemund et al. 2020). Just after birth, the newborn needs to be fed with a nasogastric tube. It should be explained to them that the child has no problems with mental development, that this abnormality has been successfully treated, and the child will lead a completely normal life (Rogers 1976; Parham et al. 2023).

The surgery for the cleft lip and the soft palate will be performed in the first 3–6 months of life as in the presented case, and the hard palate cleft will be surgically treated between the 3rd and 6th year, depending on the orthodontic treatment and growth of the maxilla. In the meantime, a team of specialists will take care of the child. This team includes a fetal morphologist, maxillofacial surgeon, speech therapist, psychologist, orthodontist, pediatrician, and plastic surgeon for further operations or interventions. We can confidently say that the treatment of this anomaly is very complex.

Home message: Increasing the competence of health professionals and the level of health literacy among the population will allow the implementation of preventive measures and improved prenatal care. Early detection and surgical intervention and timely treatment can improve the quality of life of children born with cleft lip and palate, highlighting the importance of increased efforts to reduce the impact of risk factors and ultimately improve the well-being of affected individuals and their families.

Conclusion

Knowledge of the risk factors for the occurrence of cleft lip and palate will allow the implementation of preventive measures, and early diagnosis and management and treatment by a multidisciplinary team can improve the quality of life of children affected by this condition and ensure that their families receive the appropriate care and support they need.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors certify that there is no conflict of interest with any financial organization regarding the material discussed in the manuscript.

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Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

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Author contributions

All authors contributed to the manuscript and read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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